

A finite element model of component solution space for early stage design uncertainties

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Abstract

This work proposes a new method for testing a component for crashworthiness in a new car early development phase. The method accounts for the relations between components to assess how the development uncertainties (i.e. epistemic uncertainties) affect the performance of the one currently tested. Common tests, like a drop tower set-up, fail at capturing how other components can affect the performance itself. Hence, we propose a new Finite Elements simplified model where all components involved in a frontal crash are represented. To capture these relations, we couple 1D elements with the full mesh of the component to study. Solution Space, then, characterizes all uncertainties. These are inputs to the 1D element behavior. Running 10,000 samples confirms the method to work: the simulations are stable, and we capture how one component is affected by the others. When still no design is available for other parts, developers now have a new tool to test how robust their design is in relation to the interactions with these unknown other components.

1 Introduction

The development of new vehicles is a complex process that involves many iterations to find the best design compliant with all requirements. This entire process is characterized by many uncertain factors, forcing car manufacturers to use methods for cascading high-level requirements to component's level and guide developers make robust decisions. One of these methods is the Solution Space approach [1]. It translates the crashworthiness requirements to a set of intervals or force values that a structural component needs to meet during an accident. Such intervals — called Solution Space Corridors — not only guarantee a design to be crashworthy, but also allow each structural component to be designed independently of others while allowing enough flexibility to developers. Developers are then required to stay within the corridors' limits with their components. Given this requirement, we can consider Solution Space a way of characterizing uncertainty on the development process and cascade this uncertainty on an early-phase design of structural components. We propose a method for designers to understand if their early designs are robust enough in relation to the other components when they still have little or no information available on these.

To create a new testing environment, we take advantage of recent developments in the field of single component testing using 1D elements to input the uncertainty coming from other components [2]. In [2] the uncertainty represents what is happening at the end of the component, thus focusing on how forces are transmitted at the interface. On the contrary, here we look at the problem from a more global point of view: we study the interactions between all components, even if they are not directly connected. We, thus, do not capture how components act on adjacent ones, but we gain how components on other loadpaths can affect our design.

In this paper we start by giving a brief introduction on Solution Space, how 1D elements are used in FE simulations, and the sampling method. We then introduce the method we propose along with some evidence to show its applicability, and finally we reflect on the strengths and weaknesses of the method itself.

1.1 Component test

We, first, provide the reader a quick overview of the current common practices for testing components, as means for comparison with our method. These are: quasi-static and dynamic tests. The first consists in slowly crushing the component under a press. The energy provided to the press corresponds to the energy absorbed by the component itself; this energy is, generally, mapped against the crushing length. Examples of this type of testing can be traced back to the work of Alexander et al. [3]. The second test, on the other hand, accelerates an impactor — a rigidbody with a fixed mass — until it impacts and crushes the component. These tests manage to replicate dynamic effects, like those linked to shock waves. Examples of this type of testing are [4].

A shortcoming of both tests has already been pointed out by Van Mierlo et al. in [2]: the boundary conditions little resemble the actual conditions during a car accident. Van Mierlo et al. introduced 1D elements at the end of the component to characterize how other components interact with the one tested and effectively showed that the performance is affected. In the present work, however, we assume to not have enough information on local interaction. The method we are proposing uses Solution Space to have global knowledge on other components. Solution Space characterizes also components on other loadpaths, hence, unlike [2], we can study how the relation between different load paths can affect the component performance.

1.2 Solution Space Methods

Zimmermann et al. introduced the Solution Space approach to independently develop different components in [1]. Their work was then further developed by Fender et al. [5], Graff et al. [6], and, more recently, by Vogt et al. [7], and Daub and others [8, 9, 10]. The work presented in this paper takes advantage of the application developed by Daub on Component Solution Space in relation to the 2011 Honda Accord [8]. In it, the author computes the Solution Space Corridors for the frontal structure; what follows is a short summary of this work.

In [8], the Solution Space Corridors are expressed in an n -dimensional space where each dimension expresses a force-deformation relation. To compute these relations, the first step is expressing this force-deformation relation by assessing how much each component deforms by computing the Geometry Space Model and the Deformation Space Model introduced by Lange et al. in [11]; once you define the relation between all relevant components — the Geometry Space Model — one can compute their deformation length. This step defines how much each component contributes to the total crush length, resulting in the Deformation Space Model. Here, components are divided into sections of fixed deformation length. The average force over each section represents a variable of the Solution Space mathematical formulation.

In the following step, we consider the mathematical space Ω described by the said variables and its subspace — the feasible solutions subspace — defined by the mathematical translation of the crashworthiness requirements:

- Maximum deceleration a_c — during the whole crash the vehicle must not exceed the deceleration of 300 m/s^2 ; $\frac{F(x)}{m(x)} \leq a_c = 300 \text{ m/s}^2$, where $F(x)$ is the force absorbed by the vehicle and $m(x)$ the mass of the vehicle itself;
- Order of deformation — the components must deform in a predefined order, first those at the front bumper and last the ones at the firewall; thus, if the force of the first component is F_i and the one of the next component is F_{i+1} , it stands that $F_i \leq F_{i+1}$;
- Minimum energy absorption — the front structure must absorb at least the energy corresponding to the initial velocity v_0 of 15.6 m/s ; $-\int_{s_0}^{s_{n_{sec}}} \frac{F(x)}{m(x)} dx \leq -\frac{1}{2}v_0^2$, where s_0 is the component deformation corresponding to the first corridor and $s_{n_{sec}}$ is the component deformation corresponding to the last section.

To guarantee the independence between all sections, Component Solution Space computes the biggest hypercube — volume wise — one could fit in the feasible solution subspace. The hypercube guarantees the independence of each section, the maximum possible design flexibility, and the possibility to easily visualize the Solution Space Corridors as intervals on a 2D force-deformation plane. Before moving to an overview on

methods used to reduce the vehicle model with 1D elements, we remark once more the two major properties of the Solution Space:

- If the crush force of all sections does not exceed the limits of the solution space corridors, the overall design fulfils all three crashworthiness requirements;
- Each section has a solution space corridor independent of others, hence, all components can be designed independently of each other.

1.3 1D elements

Another key feature of this work is using 1D elements coupled with full FE meshes. This is a well-established procedure in the field of crash simulation to reduce the order of the model. Some of the different approaches available are summarized in this section.

The first method we present is the one developed by Halgrin et al. in [12]. The authors took advantage of the findings of Wierzbicki and Abramowicz — see [13] — to formulate a new type of beam: the formulation matches the behavior of a circular or rectangular bar that deforms axially. This approach, however, works only for the type of cross-section specified in the beam formulation. The second approach we present involves measuring the component response in a crash simulation and then impose the measured behavior to a beam element. It allows to closely map the behavior of the component to be replaced, like in Fender's example in [14]. This method's downside is that you first need to run a full simulation to measure your data. Further possibilities to create low-fidelity models for crash are summarized e.g. in [15]

Our method is intended for early phase development; we suppose that we are not able to run a full car simulation. However, we use the second approach because we want to precisely impose the behavior defined by the Solution Space Corridors.

1.4 Sampling Methods

The last tool needed before diving in the method itself is a powerful sampling technique to cover as much of the design space as possible. While a huge variety of methods and space-filling criteria have been developed — see for example [16] for a review — we focus mainly on the method chosen for this work. It is based on the Sobol sampling, part of the class of Quasi Monte Carlo methods (e.g. [17]). As an adaptation of the Monte Carlo sampling, this class of methods places samples quasi-randomly based on low-discrepancy sequences of prime numbers. This reduces common problems with Monte Carlo sampling, such as the lumping of sample points. To further reduce Quasi Monte Carlo related problems — like those presented in [18, 19, 20] — we use the sampling method proposed by Komeilizadeh et al. in [21, 22]: Isovolumetric Sampling. This method favors placing samples towards the boundary of the design space since this region has the biggest share of the volume in high dimensional cases. The concept shows promising results in space-filling criteria and has been successfully applied to optimization problems in crashworthiness [23]. As we will see in the next section, the capability of isovolumetric sampling to handle high dimensionality is of fundamental importance.

2 Method

Let us now look in detail at the method we are proposing: firstly and briefly how we compute the Solution Space Corridors for the 2011 Honda Accord [24]. For the details, refer once again to Marco Daub's thesis [8]. Out of all the components that make the front of the car, seven are considered of structural importance for the crash performance — see Figure 1. These are then represented in the Geometry Space Model, shown in Figure 2; they belong to two different loadpaths without any form of connection, if not at the firewall. Following Lange's procedure [11], from the Geometry Space Model we obtain the Deformation Space Model. As shown in Figure 3, the components in the latter model are reduced to only their deformation lengths and they are divided into sections — each spanning over a fixed deformation length. The last step computes the Solution Space Corridors; they are shown in Figure 4. We now have 31 intervals within which

Figure 1: Solution Space modeling step 1: identify the loadpaths and their structural components

Figure 2: Solution Space modeling step 2: compute the Geometry Space Model [8]

the components' performance can vary. Each interval is later used as a variable for sampling to characterize the uncertainty linked to the development process. We now need a method to cascade this on a component we want to develop.

2.1 Finite Element Model

Once we have Solution Space Corridors — used to characterize the process uncertainty — we need a low-fidelity model to represent them in our FE model: we propose to use 1D elements. As already said, we couple 1D elements with an early-stage high-fidelity model of the component we are currently interested studying.

The high-fidelity model has a total length that consists of both its deformable and undeformable part. This forces us to represent in the low-fidelity model for both, the deformable and the undeformable parts. The first is represented using the LS-Dyna material card MAT_068 Non-Linear-Plastic-discrete-beam with the

Figure 3: Solution Space modeling step 3: derive the Deformation Space Model [8]

Figure 4: Solution Space results [8]

Table 1: Components characteristics used for modeling 1D elements

Component Number [-]	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Deformable length [mm]	313	156	78	54	101	150	270
Deformable length [%]	76	62	11	47	57	59	50
Undeformable length [mm]	99	94	640	61	77	105	270
Undeformable length [%]	24	38	89	53	43	41	50
Total [mm]	412	250	718	115	178	255	540

following parameters citeLSDYNA: mass density $\rho = 7.89E - 09$ ton/mm³, translational stiffness $k = 2.07E + 05$ N/mm, and plastic behavior defined by step curves derived from the Solution Space Corridors — for details see [25]. The undeformable part, on the other hand, is modeled as a rigid part: a very stiff spring modeled with MAT_066 and a translational stiffness two orders of magnitude bigger than the one chosen for the deformable part. Notice that also parameters like the component volume is split into these two parts as detailed in Table 1. For example, component 1 has a deformable length of 313 mm which accounts for 76% of the total length, hence 76% of the total mass is assigned to the deformable part and the rest to the undeformable part. Lastly, to couple the low-fidelity model — the 1D elements — with the high-fidelity model we use Constrained Nodal Rigid Bodies; the nodes at the interface between the two parts are rigidly linked together.

As proposed in Daub’s work, we add a third loadpath to account for all other sources of energy dissipation. We, however, use a different formulation: the force-deformation behavior is computed from the difference between the energy absorbed by the full car (E_{tot}) and the energy absorbed only by the two loadpaths (E_{prt}). Mathematically, at each $i - th$ timestep:

$$F_i = \alpha \frac{\Delta E}{\Delta d} = \alpha \frac{(E_{tot}^i - E_{prt}^i) + (E_{tot}^{i-1} - E_{prt}^{i-1})}{(d^i - d^{i-1})}. \quad (1)$$

In this equation, d^i is the displacement at the $i - th$ timestep, whereas the factor α is a corrective factor equal to 2 to increase the fidelity of this extra beam. Figure 5 shows an example of the model obtained with the methodology just described. The model is then fixed on one side and crushed on the other by a rigid wall with a total mass of 1.12 ton, corresponding to the mass of the vehicle without the front part, and an initial velocity of 15.6 m/s.

Before looking at an application, we provide a couple of final remarks. Since we are re-designing the Honda Accord and we are dealing with a low-fidelity model, we consider acceptable to use information from the Honda Accord model itself. These information can, generally speaking, be obtained from previous cars or cars similar to the one under development. On top of this, we also simulated only half of the model, to reduce the computational effort.

Figure 5: FE model coupling 1D elements representing the Geometry Space Model and high-fidelity mesh of component 6

Figure 6: Results of the 10,000 simulations: the original behavior in grey and the maximum and minimum bound of the variability area in black

3 Application Example

To assess if the method we are proposing is working we need, on one side, to check the stability of the model itself, and on the other, to analyze if the outcome is the expected one. Both can be achieved by sampling within the design space and running the respective simulations. Therefore, we set up a model for component 6, shown in Figure 5, and use the sampling technique presented in Section 1.4. Notice that component 6 is 4 sections long, thus the model of Figure 5 is representing only 27 of the 31 sections of the Solution Space.

We run a total of 10,000 simulations, all successful and distributed across the 27-dimensional subspace defined by the Solution Space. For each simulation, we then measure the force-deformation curve; however, in Figure 6 we show only the maximum and minimum values — the black curves — measured per deformation. Let us compare the drop-tower test — the grey curve — and the black curves of Figure 6: as expected the performance of component 6 is influenced by the other components. We can, therefore, conclude that having a stable FE model and having results in line with our expectations indicate that the method proposed here works.

3.1 Discussion

Before concluding, we take a few words to discuss the method we proposed and assess its strengths and weaknesses. Firstly, our technique provides a methodology that, like the method presented by Van Mierlo et al. in [2], can couple together different components involved in a crash. Where Van Mierlo's work captures local interactions, we capture global ones: we characterize the relation between components deforming in parallel and not physically connected. Although this can be a powerful tool, it is greatly limited by the curse of dimensionality. Inherently, Solution Space yields a high number of independent sections, thus a high number of variables in the uncertainty model. In our case study, we have 27 independent variables. We focus this work only on assessing whether the method itself works. Before properly cascading the process uncertainty defined by the Solution Space one should first better investigate the type of uncertainty and then reduce the problem dimensionality. To improve the method, we suggest two possibilities:

1. Reduce the loadpaths to an interface at the component level, thus capturing the entire uncertainty with few 1D elements to replicate both, what is being deformed in series and in parallel;
2. Study the physical dependencies within a component and introduce these relations between the component's sections.

Both methods have advantages and drawbacks, but they both require a more in-depth study of the components. This, along with studying the relation between input and output, falls out of the scope of this work.

4 Conclusion

In this work we take a well-known method for reducing the order of a car model — coupling 1D elements with high-fidelity meshes — to enhance single component tests. We represent with a FE model the Geometry Space Model — previously shown in Figure 2 — of the Honda Accord. Thanks to this representation we are able to use the Solution Space Corridors to characterize the uncertainty linked to the development process and introduce it in a component early development phase. We then test the methodology on one of the seven structural components: number 6 in Figure 1. As shown in Figure 6, the method is successful: we capture how a component performance is affected by other components and loadpaths. Our methodology provides developers with a way for understanding how their newly developed design is affected by the performance of other components when these are still not ready; ultimately, a designer is from the very beginning provided with information generally not available at such an early stage of development. This means we address a certain type of epistemic uncertainty normally not covered by established methods.

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